

**THE INFLUENCE OF EASE OF USE, FREE SHIPPING, AND CUSTOMER REVIEWS ON
PURCHASE DECISIONS IN E-COMMERCE (A CASE STUDY ON STUDENTS OF THE
ENTREPRENEURSHIP STUDY PROGRAM AT FEB UNM)**

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Abstract

This study aims to determine whether the variables of Convenience, Free Shipping, and Customer Reviews have a simultaneous or partial effect on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce among Entrepreneurship Program Students at FEB UNM. This research is a quantitative study with the independent variables of Convenience (X1), Free Shipping (X2), and Customer Review (X3), while the dependent variable is Purchase Decision on E-Commerce (Y). The population in this study consists of active students of the Entrepreneurship Study Program at FEB UNM from the 2021-2023 cohort, with a sample of 50 student respondents who have previously transacted on e-commerce using a non-probability sampling technique with the accidental sampling method. The data analysis used classical assumption tests with normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test; as well as hypothesis tests with multiple linear regression, simultaneous test, partial test, and coefficient of determination test. Based on the data processing results through SPSS, the partial test results show that only the customer review variable has a partial influence on purchasing decisions in e-commerce, while the convenience and free shipping variables do not have a partial influence. Therefore, the first and second hypotheses in this study are rejected, and the third hypothesis is accepted. Meanwhile, the regression constant

value is positive and the *F*-calculated value is greater than the *F*-table value, so the three variables simultaneously influence the purchasing decision on e-commerce with a coefficient of determination value of 0.354, and the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted.

Keywords : E-Commerce, Purchase Decision, Convenience, Free Shipping, Customer Review, Students, Entrepreneurship.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of technology that unites the world has now become one of the biggest factors in changing consumer purchasing patterns. While connected to the internet, consumers can purchase products online anywhere and anytime (Putri, 2021).

The development of technology and changes in purchasing patterns are what then drive increasingly fierce competition in the business and economic world. The change in purchasing patterns is supported by the increasingly diverse needs of society, which then introduces the habit of shopping online, also known as online shopping. This is what then triggers the development of market systems using the internet media, more commonly known as e-commerce (Maulana & Asra, 2019).

The high popularity of e-commerce today has triggered the emergence of various online stores in Indonesia, making the competition among these e-commerce platforms increasingly fierce (Putri, 2021).

Table of the Competition Among the 5 Largest E-Commerce Platforms in Indonesia, Q1 2023

NO.	E-commerce Name	Average Monthly Site Visits
1	Shopee	157.966.666,67
2	Tokopedia	117.033.333,33
3	Lazada	83.233.333,33
4	Blibli	25.433.333,33
5	Bukalapak	18.066.666,67

Source: Databoks (2023)

Based on the data in table above, it can be concluded that every month, many people visit e-commerce sites, with the highest number of visits on Shopee, followed by Tokopedia. Meanwhile, Lazada became the e-commerce platform with the third-highest average monthly site visitors in the first quarter of 2023, followed by Blibli, and the one with the smallest average monthly site visitors among the five e-commerce platforms was Bukalapak. This shows that the existence of e-commerce in Indonesia has become a continuously growing trend.

The increasing proliferation of e-commerce is also creating intense competition for business players to attract potential consumers. Understanding and knowledge of consumer behavior can be the first step for business actors to attract the attention of potential consumers.

Consumer behavior can be defined as the behavior exhibited by consumers or buyers in terms of searching for products and services, purchasing, using, evaluating, and consuming products and services that buyers expect to fulfill their desires (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2010:07).

Knowledge and understanding of consumer behavior is not an easy task, as it involves many influencing factors that interact with each other. Therefore, the marketing approach adopted by a company must be meticulously designed and planned, taking these factors into account. In addition, business practitioners must be able to understand consumers and strive to identify how consumers behave, act, and think. Although consumers have various differences, they also have many similarities.

Business actors should be able to understand the diversity and similarities of consumers or consumer behavior so that they can market their products effectively. Business actors need to understand why and how a consumer makes a purchasing decision so that they can formulate better marketing strategies. Businesspeople who understand consumer behavior will be able to predict how consumers are likely to react to the information they receive. This results in business actors being able to design efficient marketing strategies. It cannot be denied that business actors who understand and comprehend consumers will be able to compete.

The purchasing decision becomes an important component for companies to pay attention to because consumers tend to consider many factors before making a purchase, including their

own needs. The purchase decision is a stage where consumers truly decide to buy. According to Tjiptono (2012), the purchase decision is a process in which consumers identify their problems, gather information about certain products or brands, and evaluate each alternative to see if it can solve the identified problem, which then leads to the purchase decision.

There are three indicators of purchase decisions according to Devaraj et al. (2003), namely search efficiency (requiring a short time, facilitating in usage, as well as facilitating search); value (having competitive prices and good quality); and interaction (information, security, load time, and navigation).

Various strategies are vigorously implemented by business actors, which emerge from their understanding of consumer behavior. There are various forms of strategies implemented by e-commerce business actors to attract the attention and purchasing interest of potential consumers, some of which include convenience, free shipping, and the provision of Customer Review features as a product rating tool by consumers who use the product. With the implementation of these strategies, it is hoped that they can influence consumer purchasing decisions and lead to purchases.

Ease of use is one of the factors that consumers consider. The ease of use offered can be considered successful if the system can be used as easily as possible without processes that burden its users. Consumers believe in the existence of an information system that is easy to understand, more flexible, and easy to operate. The ease of use of the application also becomes an important aspect that e-commerce providers need to pay attention to, considering that e-commerce buyers have varying levels of ease, ranging from ease in accessing product options, ease in making purchases, ease in payment transactions, to ease in receiving goods. According to Venkatesh and Davis (2000), the indicators of ease are easy to use; easy learnable (easy to learn); clear and understandable (clear and understandable); easy to become skillful (easy to become skillful); controllable (controllable); and flexible (flexible).

The provision of free shipping is one of the strategies implemented by e-commerce to attract potential consumers by offering a policy that allows them to shop online without having to pay for shipping costs. According to (Maharani et al., 2022), the provision of free shipping has become one of the factors that attract public enthusiasm for shopping through e-commerce, thereby having a significant impact on the purchasing decisions of the public through e-commerce. According to Sari (2019), there are four indicators of free shipping in influencing purchase decisions, namely free shipping attracts attention; free shipping has appeal; free shipping stimulates the desire to buy; and free shipping encourages making a purchase.

Customer reviews can create and encourage consumers to decide to make a purchase. According to Latief and Ayustira (2020), online customer review (OCR) can be defined as a means that allows consumers to freely and easily write their opinions or reviews online about various products or services. Customer reviews that are widely uploaded on various products and services have become part of the decision-making process for many consumers. Latief & Ayustira (2020) explain that product data is more reliable and necessary in the context of online shopping to support decision-making.

purchase. The data is offered and considered credible and trustworthy. Therefore, customer reviews can be used as a tool to gain consumer confidence. Lupiyoadi (2015) mentions that there are three indicators of online customer reviews, namely consumers obtaining information about the product; consumers being encouraged to make a purchase due to motivation obtained from others; and consumers receiving recommendations from others.

The three aspects discussed above certainly become strategies for business actors to stimulate consumers to decide to make a purchase as a form of business anticipation in attracting consumers by influencing their purchasing decisions. This highlights that knowledge and understanding of purchasing decisions are essential for supporting the sustainability and

success of a business.

Entrepreneurship students are higher education students equipped with an entrepreneurial spirit and knowledge about consumer behavior and purchasing decisions. Not excluding entrepreneurship students at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Makassar State University. Although they hold the title of entrepreneurship students, it is still possible for entrepreneurship students to occupy the position and role of a consumer in a business. Then how do these business actors' strategies apply in influencing purchasing decisions when the potential consumer is an entrepreneurship student, specifically the entrepreneurship program students of FEB UNM in this study.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a quantitative research method in which the variables, symptoms, or conditions being studied are described as they are and use numerical data obtained through surveys or questionnaires.

According to Sugiyono (2013), a population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that possess certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then concluded. In this study, the population used is the Entrepreneurship Study Program students of FEB UNM batch 2021-2023 who have made product purchases through e-commerce. The author chose this population due to their curiosity about the attitudes of students who, by nature, are equipped with entrepreneurial knowledge in making purchasing decisions on e-commerce. The population in this study consists of 293 students, which includes 60 students from the 2021 cohort, 95 students from the 2022 cohort, and 138 students from the 2023 cohort.

A sample is a part of a population that consists of several members of the population. In other words, a sample is a representative of the population. In this study, the author uses a nonprobability sampling technique, which is a sampling method that does not give every member of the population an equal chance to be selected as a sample. Meanwhile, the technique for determining the number of respondents was carried out using the accidental sampling method, which is a sampling technique that selects respondents encountered by chance. However, these potential respondents must meet certain characteristics, namely they must be students of the Entrepreneurship Study Program at FEB UNM who have made product purchases on e-commerce platforms.

This research instrument is measured using a questionnaire regarding the influence of convenience, free shipping, and customer reviews on purchasing decisions in e-commerce, with a number of questions for respondents to answer. The research instrument is outlined in the form of indicators so that the study has direction in formulating questions.

This research is measured using a Likert scale, which can be used to assess the opinions, attitudes, and perceptions of an individual or a group of people regarding social phenomena.

According to Sugiyono (2013), this questionnaire provides four alternative answers: strongly agree (SA) with a score of 4, agree (A) with a score of 3, disagree (D) with a score of 2, and strongly disagree (SD) with a score of 1.

Multiple linear regression analysis is an analysis to measure the magnitude of the influence between two or more independent variables on one dependent variable and to predict the dependent variable using the independent variables, as well as to predict the value of the independent variables using the dependent variable. In a regression analysis, the dependent

variable serves to provide explanation (explanatory), while the independent variable functions as the object being explained (the explained).

In this study, there are three independent variables, namely the convenience factor (X_1), the free shipping factor (X_2), and the customer review factor (X_3), which will be examined for their influence on one dependent variable, namely the purchasing decision on e-commerce (Y).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Sangadji and Sopiah (2013:24-26) state that a consumer's purchasing decision can be influenced by several factors, namely psychological factors, situational factors, and social factors. Situational factors are all the elements attached to the store that then shape the conditions perceived and felt by consumers during the shopping transaction. In e-commerce, its ease of use, the availability of free shipping promotions, and customer review features are aspects that are inherent and provided by e-commerce to encourage consumers to make purchases.

1. The Influence of Convenience on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce

Based on the research results, the regression coefficient for the Ease variable (X_1) on the E-Commerce Purchase Decision variable (Y) is 0.103, indicating that the Ease factor (X_1) has a positive influence on the E-Commerce Purchase Decision (Y).

Meanwhile, the t-statistic value for this variable is 1.293, which is smaller than the t-table value (2.011), so it can be stated that the influence given by the Ease variable (X_1) on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce (Y) is not significant. This is because students of the Entrepreneurship Study Program at FEB UNM do not prioritize how easy a platform is to use and access as a consideration in making a purchase decision.

The results of this study can be said to indicate that the Ease factor has a positive but not significant effect on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce, which aligns with the findings of Satvika Ruri and Astuti Purnamawati (2022) who concluded that the ease of use factor positively affects purchase decisions. However, it can be said to be less in line with the research by Evelyn Wijaya and Warnadi (2019) which concluded that the ease of use factor has a positive and significant effect, as well as the research by I Gusti Ngurah Satria Wijaya et al. (2022) which concluded that the influence generated by the perception of ease on purchasing decisions is significant.

2. The Influence of Free Shipping on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce

Based on the research results, the regression coefficient for the Free Shipping variable (X_2) on the E-Commerce Purchase Decision variable (Y) is -0.015, indicating that the Free Shipping factor (X_2) does not have a positive influence on the E-Commerce Purchase Decision (Y). Meanwhile, the t-value for this variable is -0.154, which is smaller than the t-table value (2.011), thus it can be stated that the influence given by the Free Shipping variable (X_2) on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce (Y) is not significant. This happens because Entrepreneurship Program students are not deterred by shipping costs when they intend to purchase a product through e-commerce.

The results of this study can then be said that the Free Shipping factor does not have a positive or significant impact on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce, thus it is stated to be inconsistent with previous research by Hutomo Atman Maulana and Yunelly Asra (2019) as well as research by Dara Melfaliza and Ahmad Nizam (2022) which both found that the free shipping factor has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions.

3. The Influence of Customer Reviews on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce

Based on the research results, the regression coefficient for the Customer Review variable (X_3) on the E-Commerce Purchase Decision variable (Y) is 0.453, indicating that the Customer Review factor (X_3) has a positive influence on the E-Commerce Purchase Decision (Y).

Meanwhile, the t-statistic value for this variable is 3.292, which is greater than the t-table value (2.011), indicating that the influence of the Customer Review variable (X_3) on the Purchase Decision in E-Commerce (Y) is significant. This is because students of the Entrepreneurship Study Program at FEB UNM are very meticulous about the products they are going to buy. through e-commerce, so they pay close attention to positive reviews from previous customers on e-commerce.

The results of this study indicate that the Customer Review factor has a positive and significant impact on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce, which aligns with the findings of research by Ety Zuliawati Zed et al. (2023) and research by Dara Melfaliza and Ahmad Nizam (2022), both of which concluded that the customer review factor has a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions.

4. The Influence of Convenience, Free Shipping, and Customer Reviews on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce

Based on the research results, the obtained multiple regression constant is 2.075, which indicates that the three variables, namely Ease (X_1), Free Shipping (X_2), and Customer Review (X_3), simultaneously have a positive influence on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce (Y). Meanwhile, the R^2 value obtained is 0.354, which indicates that these three variables influence Purchase Decisions on E-Commerce by 35.4%, and the remaining 64.6% is influenced by other factors. This is because students of the Entrepreneurship Study Program at FEB UNM tend to shop by considering these three factors simultaneously, where they choose e-commerce that is easy to use, offers free shipping, and has customer review features that can convince them to make a purchase.

The results of this study are in line with previous research by Siti Robiah (2023), which concluded that the factors of convenience and customer reviews simultaneously influence purchase decisions in e-commerce along with flash sales. The results of this study are also in line with the research by Hutomo Atman Maulana (2019), which concluded that free shipping affects purchasing decisions in e-commerce.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results involving 50 active students from the Entrepreneurship Study Program at FEB UNM batch 2021-2023, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. The Ease Factor (X_1) does not have a partial effect on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce (Y), thus the hypothesis is rejected.
2. The Free Shipping Factor (X_2) does not have a partial effect on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce (Y), so the hypothesis is rejected.
3. The Customer Review factor (X_3) has a partial effect on Purchase Decisions in E-Commerce (Y), thus the hypothesis is accepted.
4. The Ease Factor (X_1), Free Shipping (X_2), and Customer Review (X_3) simultaneously influence Purchase Decisions on E-Commerce (Y), thus the hypothesis is accepted.

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